

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO THE ROLE OF READING AND LIBRARIES IN THE PROCESS OF OBTAINING INFORMATION BY THE YOUTH OF UZBEKISTAN.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8133416>

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Abstract

The article reveals the socio-philosophical point of view of the author on the problems of the development of reading culture, which is considered relevant in modern society, and an attempt is made to objectively analyze the phenomenon of reading culture among young people, focuses on the formation and development of reading culture among young people. It is noted that the phenomenon of reading culture is one of the little-studied areas. And the issues of the formation of the reading culture of young people have not been studied as a complex object of study.

Key words

Book love and reading, literacy, "reading crisis", book production, information and library centers, information resource centers

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan has entered a new stage of development based on the principle "From national revival to national rise". The intensity of the new era is aimed at establishing good values and traditions in the life of society, especially in raising the spiritual and intellectual potential of our people, especially the young generation, their thinking and worldview, and raising a well-rounded person who lives with love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people. is doing.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

This article is a national program for the development and support of reading culture for 2020-2025 [1] Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On State Policy Regarding Youth", Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Information-Library Activities", decrees, decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Prepared in accordance with government decisions and other legal documents and universal norms of international law. In the article, on the basis of the analysis of national and advanced foreign experience in the field of reading, issues related to

the development and support of reading culture in Uzbekistan to a new level, creation, printing, delivery of book products, popularization of reading, scientific and methodological provision, training of personnel, management of reading infrastructure covered.

RESULTS

Education is a very ancient process, and many scientific research works are dedicated to studying its role and importance in human life. Without dwelling on the history of the research of educational processes, if we illuminate today's educational models, the following can be distinguished:

- 1) the model of education as a shaper of the scientific landscape of the world ;
- 2) the model of education as a shaper of thinking culture ;
- 3) the model of education as a school of life ;
- 4) the model of education as a career guide .

Currently, in many countries, such a situation is observed that in the next decades, in the educational system of developed countries, special importance is given to the study of applied sciences, and more attention is paid to the training of practical specialists rather than scientific researchers. Pragmatic Americans are focusing more on practical subjects, devoting enough hours to basic subjects for the overall development of the child. In Great Britain, due to dissatisfaction with educational outcomes, reforms in 1988 began to focus more on education-industry links. After all, the industry is the main customer and consumer of the education system. In France, too, vocational orientation of universities is at the center of educational reforms. 90% of the graduates of basic and real schools in the GFR receive dual education, that is, they improve professional skills in the organization and receive theoretical education in vocational schools. A similar tendency has recently appeared in Russia: there is talk of reducing compulsory subjects in education and introducing subjects of study according to the choice of students. Today, in the formation of the culture of reading in educational institutions, there are several situations related to the reception and assimilation of information by students, and it is necessary to solve the problems related to these situations and to widely promote positive experience. One of such problems is the problem of text complexity. It is impossible to ignore what kind of books young people are reading. It is known that any text contains certain information. How to convey this information to the reader depends on the skill of the author of the text. At first glance, this issue is mainly dealt with by textologists and stylistic experts. Also, depending on the text type, genre, and other characteristics, linguists, literary scholars, and historians conduct research. But the reader chooses specific literature

based on his needs, learns it depending on his goals, level of physical and mental preparation and capabilities. This complex activity occurs during the reading process. This aspect shows that it is necessary to study the individual's activity in detail. This is clearly shown by the activities aimed at the fundamental reform of education in our republic. That is why the scientific approach to any means and resources related to the comprehensive development of a person in society is one of the urgent issues of today.

Text is an important component of the reading process. It plays a big role in forming the reading culture of a person. Therefore, the psychological and sociological aspects of the process of acceptance and perception of the text by the reader should be thoroughly researched. It also requires that specific research be conducted to help develop guidelines for its further improvement in the formation of reading culture. In this case, studying the text, the necessary information in it and the process of attracting the reader's attention to this information will help clarify the issue of reading and its improvement.

In works dedicated to the study of the philosophy and psychology of the reader [2], the main attention is focused on the individual interest, needs and goals of the person. However, for some reason, the text features, which are the necessary source and basis of the reading process, and the problems of its acceptance by the reader are being neglected. It is true that personal activity is important in the event of reading. However, we should not forget that it is important to clarify the issue of the source of motivation for this activity - the features of the text and to what extent it affects the reader. In particular, in order to improve this process, it is necessary to create research aimed at raising it to higher levels.

A librarian helps the reader select books based on their needs, and copywriters work to make their products appealing to the reader. In other words, librarians, teachers, parents, social institutions, as well as all state and non-state organizations related to the development of the individual and his/her development participate in the delivery of the product created by the authors of the text to the consumer based on their capabilities and existing requirements. Philosophical, psychological and sociological study of this complex and at the same time important process is important in improving reading culture today. In a word, they should understand that the main goal is to bring up a mature generation, the main means are subjects and objects that help it, and the main source is the texts created for reading. As the text is, so is its consumer. But how to receive the text in this place also depends on the level of preparation of the consumer and the relationship of the tools that help him.

The main sources of reading for young people today are, of course, the sources of information they learn, textbooks and training manuals. In our country, significant work has been done to ensure freedom of speech, to reorganize the management system of the information and mass communications sector, and to increase the role of mass media in solving the problematic issues of socio-political and socio-economic development.

At the same time, the analysis of the current situation in the field shows that there is no prompt and adequate response to the challenges arising in the media space, and the needs of society for the timely provision of comprehensive information about the large-scale reforms implemented in the country require a significant increase in the work in the information field, the information services of state bodies and organizations, requires bringing the activities of mass media to a new level in terms of quality.

In the current conditions of the reform of the socio-economic sphere in the republic, the goals and objectives of the development of information-library activities must be consistent with the changes taking place in the country and international practice. In this regard, to create a qualitatively new system of providing information and library services to the population, which ensures the constitutional rights of citizens to free access to information, including the enjoyment of national values and world culture, practical and fundamental knowledge, preservation and enrichment of the national cultural heritage kept in libraries, information - improving the organization of information-library institutions due to the wide introduction of communication technologies is becoming a priority task.

This makes it possible to have a serious impact on information-library activities, service to readers, replenishment and storage of funds, automation of library processes, scientific-research and organizational-methodical activities, training, retraining and promotion of personnel, expansion of international cooperation.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4354 dated June 7, 2019 [3] "On further improvement of information and library services to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is proof of our opinion. It sets the tasks of increasing attention, increasing its general cultural level, raising its spirituality, moral education. In today's society, information-library institutions appear as information-receiving, cultural-educational and educational institutions.

Information-library institutions of the republic with a universal fund are of special importance in the deep understanding of national culture, analysis of its

development and evolution. There is a need to raise the status of educational institutions, to develop the scientific and informational potential of network scientific information-library institutions, as well as public-private partnership in the information-library sector, and the network of private and digital (virtual) information-library institutions in the country»[4].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is necessary to eliminate the factors that have a negative effect on the acquisition of the content of the text, which is an important component of the formation of reading culture among students. This will make it easier for our young people to master the text and help them swim more freely in the ocean of knowledge.

Based on the results of the sociological research conducted in order to study the state of information-library service provision and formation of reading culture among students, a number of suggestions for improving the situation were developed. They are in several directions, the first of which concerns the strengthening of the legal and regulatory framework.

According to the results of the research, the regulatory and legal base of information resource centers of educational institutions needs further improvement. In particular, the following cases should be seriously considered:

- the introduction of separate sections in the charters of educational institutions, which define the status of information resource centers, strategic goals, and the obligations of heads of institutions to information library centers ;

- it is necessary to further process the model charter of the IKM at the educational institution, in which it is necessary to define from the goals and tasks of the IKM to the number of employees, as well as to adopt separate instructions on their activities.

The second direction is to improve the resource base of SMEs. In this case, the resource base refers to the library fund, information-search systems, cases of using information-library resources of other libraries. The analysis shows that the following problems should be solved in this direction :

- it is necessary to prevent the decrease of both the main funds and educational funds. In this, it is necessary to solve the problems of providing literature (both electronic, educational and general literature) by fields, to providing a book (or electronic resource) suitable for each student;

- The level of supply of fiction literature is lower because the educational institutions' IKMs focus on the provision of educational literature in the period of economic scarcity. However, especially in rural areas and remote districts, taking

into account the fact that educational institutions should provide services to other segments of the population, special attention should be paid to the provision of fiction, socio-political literature and electronic resources ;

- ICMs of educational institutions should be filled with pedagogical literature intended for teachers;

- It is necessary to improve the system of electronic search, catalogs and card files, which is one of the main elements of the resource base of the ICMs.

revealed that up to 60-70 % of the stock in all ICMs was reflected in alphabetical and systematic catalogs. At this point, it should be noted that the majority of librarians who participated in the research (89%) emphasized that electronic catalogs increase the efficiency of work in this regard and contribute to the development of the information culture of students. However, for this, all libraries should be fully computerized and provided with search programs.

The third direction is to improve the reading culture of teachers and students. Improving the reading culture of a person in modern society requires special training and professional influence. That is, special reading culture lessons should be included in educational institutions, especially in the educational system. Today, this process is supported by various cultural and educational events organized by the employees of the private enterprises. However, this is being done in a chaotic manner, relying on the initiatives and creativity of the employees of the Ministry of Education and Culture. The study found the following related to this condition:

- envisage the effective use of ICT of educational institutions , but do not take into account that the culture of reading is also important in raising a competent generation ;

- information of the educational system in programs resources, their search and effective use are not shown;

- improving the reading culture of students is not included in the duties of the employees of the ACM.

To sum up, there are opportunities to increase the effectiveness of the work of forming the reading culture of students in the educational institutions. In this regard, it should not be overlooked that it is necessary to use the best experiences of foreign colleagues . it is necessary to direct them in a positive direction. For this :

- introduction of special reading culture lessons in educational institutions;

- Involve the employees of the Ministry of Education and Culture to teach reading culture;

- in the eyes of the higher authorities it is necessary to organize training courses for employees of educational institutions and to introduce them to modern methods of improving the reading culture of readers.

Reading books increases the spiritual wealth of all of us, increases our conversational culture. In some cases, it is necessary to read a book to prevent some of our compatriots from becoming rude and poor due to the "service" of our sacred Uzbek language. However, our Uzbek language is one of the richest languages in the world. A.S. Pushkin used a total of 21,197 words throughout his work, while the language of Shakespeare's works used a total of more than 20,000 words. Spanish scholars reported that 18,000 words were used in Cervantes' work. The number of words used in the works of our great grandfather Alisher Navoi is more than 26,000 [5].

Undoubtedly, one of the best things created by man is the book. The book was invented it is a human achievement. Grateful people erected a statue to the book in 1976 in La Coruña, Spain .

A book is a man's friend. Nothing else can take its place in human life. What criteria and requirements does the reading in relation to this friend cover today ? In fact, what should be the reading culture?

Reading, its benefits, issues of creating reading culture in the family are discussed by our great thinkers Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Abdurauf Fitrat. and covered in the works of others. In particular, the enlightener Abdulla Avloni, who lived and created at the beginning of the 20th century, "... to strengthen our mind and perception from a young age, not to spend our precious life with idle words such as entertainment, nonsense, money , etc., but to read all kinds of books, newspapers and magazines, to open our minds, it is necessary to strengthen our mind" says [6]. We should also read books to preserve our national wealth. Changes in the socio-cultural environment and the lifestyle of the population at the end of the 20th century led to a change in the main tasks of reading, turning them into information, teaching and recreational functions. Therefore, it is becoming important to study reading processes based on new approaches, especially the systematic approach that has developed widely in sociology. In particular, it is possible to apply a systematic approach to researching the reading phenomenon of students in academic lyceums and vocational colleges operating in Uzbekistan, which are new in terms of quality. In this specialists : _

- types of reading - that it is divided into hobbies in the family, in class, outside the classroom;

- the directions of youth reading are knowledge acquisition, information acquisition, emotional-creative activity, and cultural recreation;

the funds and resources of ICMs should help adolescents in social and cultural adaptation to the period of changes ;

- ICMs should be one of the main institutions of socialization of the individual ;

- It is required to take into account the importance of theoretical analysis, not limited to studying the activities of private enterprises from the practical side .

- the system of formation of reading culture in teenagers is a complex social phenomenon, and all social institutions around it can be system-forming elements of this system. In particular, the social environment, teachers, peers, family and information resource centers play an important role in this system;

- today, the main areas of interest of teenagers are literature on history, literature on linguistics (focused on learning different languages, especially English), literature on information technology, fiction (adventure, fantastic works, romantic stories and novels, poetry), literature on sports, literature on selected fields (economics, law, medicine), partly on specific sciences (physics and mathematics);[7]

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